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20 Annual Review

25

Impact, highlights, and partnerships

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Vulture Conservation Foundation

We are the **leading non-profit organization** dedicated to the conservation of **Europe's vulture species**: the Bearded, Griffon, Cinereous, Egyptian vultures, and the increasingly present Rüppell's Vulture.

We work through *science-driven projects, international collaborations, and strong community engagement*. We work with governments, businesses, local communities, and NGOs to develop and deliver conservation initiatives grounded in the best available science, tailored to each vulture's behaviour and ecology, the threats they face, and the habitats they depend on.

Today, we lead vulture conservation across Europe and coordinate the **Bearded Vulture captive-breeding network** on behalf of EAZA's European Endangered Species Programme (EEP).

As the leading wildlife conservation organization solely committed to protecting, conserving, and restoring Europe's vulture species, we leverage our decades-long experience and expertise in *captive breeding, threat mitigation, reintroduction and restocking, monitoring, research, and advocacy* to ensure vultures continue playing their essential role in European ecosystems and beyond.

Our Mission

VCF works for the recovery of vultures and their ecosystems in Europe by *initiating, facilitating, and building capacity for science-based and long-lasting conservation actions and research.*

VCF shares its technical expertise and practical knowledge with partners from local and national governments, civil society, and international organisations to *raise awareness and support* for the essential role that vultures play in our ecosystems.

Our Vision

European vulture populations are *healthy and thriving.*

Each species reaches a good conservation status and occupies most of their former ranges, supported by good quality habitats and valued by people.

Recovery is possible - and 2025 proved it

As we reflect on 2025, I am struck above all by the power of **partnership**. The work of the Vulture Conservation Foundation has always been rooted in collaboration — with governments, NGOs, scientists, field practitioners, and local communities. This year has once again shown that when *we act together* across borders and disciplines, we can achieve results that once seemed far beyond reach.

None of this would be possible without the steadfast support of our donors. Your trust, commitment, and long-term vision help us plan beyond annual cycles and invest in the sustained conservation effort vultures need. Conservation is not built in months, but in decades — and your support makes that continuity possible.

In 2025, we strengthened our communication about vultures: sharing their ecological importance, addressing misconceptions, and bringing their stories to wider audiences. **Changing narratives** is as important as restoring populations. When people understand that vultures are essential allies in healthy ecosystems, support for their conservation grows naturally.

This year marked a historic milestone for us and for vulture conservation in Europe: the **first release of Bearded Vultures in the Balkans** — the culmination of *20 years of dedicated work* by countless partners. At the same time, we are witnessing an exponential recovery of the Cinereous Vulture population in Portugal, a powerful example of what sustained protection and reintroduction efforts can achieve. In the Alps, the Bearded Vulture population has surpassed 100 breeding pairs for the first time — a symbolic and biological threshold that few would have imagined possible a generation ago.

These achievements remind us that **recovery is possible**. With science, patience, partnership, and public support, we can restore what we once thought lost. Our work is far from finished — but in 2025, we have every reason to have faith in what the next decades may bring.

José Tavares
Director

Our Story

1978

European conservation pioneers unite with a vision to reintroduce the Bearded Vulture to the Alps. The Bearded Vulture Captive Breeding Programme starts, thanks to a grant from the Frankfurt Zoological Society.

The Guadalenin Bearded Vulture centre is established.

1996

1997

The first Bearded Vulture breeding pair in the wild in the Alps successfully raises a chick in the French Alps.

1986

The first captive-bred Bearded Vultures are released at Hohe Tauern National Park, Austria.

1992

The Foundation for the Conservation of the Bearded Vulture (FCBV) is officially launched. The Frankfurt Zoological Society cedes the 49 Bearded Vultures to the new Foundation, to expand and develop Bearded Vulture captive-breeding and conservation.

2005

The Bearded Vulture Captive Breeding Unit at the Recovery Centre Vallcalent from the Generalitat of Catalunya is established.

2009

The FCBV transforms itself into the Vulture Conservation Foundation (VCF), expanding its mission to safeguard all of Europe's vulture species.

The third VCF-led LIFE project, WildLIFE Crime Academy, is launched to strengthen national capacities to combat wildlife crime and raise awareness about this threat in Europe and North Africa.

The second VCF-lead LIFE project, LIFE Aegyptus Return, is launched to consolidate, enhance and accelerate the return of Cinereous Vultures in Portugal and Western Spain.

The first VCF-led LIFE project, BalkanDetox LIFE, is launched, to strengthen national capacities to fight wildlife poisoning and raise awareness about the problem across seven Balkan countries.

The VCF undertakes the management of the Guadalentín Bearded Vulture Captive-Breeding Centre.

The EU international species action plans for the Bearded Vulture and for the Cinereous Vulture, developed by the VCF as part of LIFE EuroSAP project, are adopted.

The Multi-species Action Plan to Conserve African-Eurasian Vultures (Vulture MsAP) - the global blueprint for vulture conservation, redacted under the co-leadership of the VCF - and the Flyway Action Plan for the Conservation of the Cinereous Vulture (CVFAP) are adopted by the CMS (Convention on Migratory Species) at COP12 (Conference of the Parties).

A meaningful year

2025 unfolded between challenges and hard-won successes.

© Bruno Berthemy

This year brought with it several historic milestones that foster hope for the future. Despite a drop in productivity within the **Bearded Vulture Captive-Breeding Network**, 17 young birds joined reintroduction programmes across Europe. Bearded Vultures **returned to Bulgaria** for the first time in over five decades. They reclaimed the **Pyrenees** through natural recolonisation. From Andalusia to Cantabria, Corsica, and the Alps, long-awaited breeding successes reminded us why we fight for these birds every single day.

The **LIFE Aegyptius Return** reached its own defining moments — among them, the landmark approval of Portugal's first private unfenced feeding area within the project framework, and the tagging of its 58th Cinereous Vulture.

Yet the year also delivered devastating blows. A **major wildfire** tore through the Douro International Natural Park, consumed nests, feeding areas, and project infrastructure, and claimed the lives of at least two, but very likely four, Cinereous Vulture chicks.

We continued supporting Griffon Vultures through our work on **LIFE projects in Croatia, Cyprus, and Sardinia**, where the species continues to expand — a sign that conservation works when communities, science, and sustained effort come together.

In Sardinia, an **Egyptian Vulture breeding pair** raised their chick successfully for the seventh consecutive year. Egyptian Vultures are also strengthening their winter presence in **Cáceres**, Spain.

©Iñigo Fajardo

We supported efforts to monitor the expansion of **Rüppell's Vultures** in Iberia. Unfortunately, of the two vultures tagged with our GPS/GSM transmitters in Morocco by JBel Moussat, only one survived.

Beyond fieldwork, we stood at the forefront of **policy, training, and research**.

This year saw a worrying focus on the true scale of **wildlife crime**, with more cases of poisoning and poaching across Europe, South Africa, and The Gambia. We refused to look away. Together with CMS Raptors MOU and BirdLife International, we led a **mission** to The Gambia, strengthening local capacity, supporting investigations, and helping shape a national action plan for vultures.

Alongside these efforts, the **WildLIFE Crime Academy** and

BalkanDetox LIFE projects marked major advances: specialised training programmes expanded to new frontiers, and Albania secured the approval of its National Action Plan against poisoning.

We were also honoured to coordinate the **International Vulture Awareness Day** for the second consecutive year, joining thousands of people across **140 events worldwide** in celebrating these extraordinary birds.

This year has tested us. It has inspired us. And above all, it has reaffirmed the **transformative power of collaboration**. As we reflect on everything 2025 has held, we extend our deepest, most heartfelt gratitude to every partner, colleague, supporter, and funder who makes this work not only possible but **meaningful**.

Vulture species in Europe

The Bearded Vulture – Europe's rarest vulture

Gypaetus barbatus

NT NEAR THREATENED

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2025 in figures

- Breeding success rate: 74% (slightly up from last year's 72%)
- Productivity: 66% (same as 2024)
- Historical release in Bulgaria, where the species has been absent for half a century.

Conservation projects

- Bearded Vulture LIFE 2023-2030 – Balkans
- LIFE Gyp'ACT 2022-2028 - French Pre-Alps and the Massif Central
- LIFE GypRescue 2021-2026 - Corsica

Bearded Vultures were once widespread across all southern and central European mountain ranges. Over the 19th and 20th centuries, they suffered a **massive decline** due to persecution, loss of food sources, and changing agricultural practices. Today, only **300 breeding pairs remain in Europe**: most in the central Pyrenees and in newly restored areas of the Alps, plus very small numbers on Corsica and Crete. Every year, young captive-bred vultures are released in the wild to support selected populations around Europe.

Threats like criminal poisoning, lead poisoning, collision with wind turbines, and electrocution on powerlines, reduced food and habitat availability, still take a toll on the species. Conservation programmes, including the ones supported by the Vulture Conservation Foundation, are relentlessly working to mitigate these threats.

Map of Bearded Vultures distribution in Europe. In bold, the areas where we contribute to Bearded Vulture reintroductions

2025 successes and challenges

The most recent monitoring showed not only population growth - breaking the **100 reproductive pairs record in the Alps** (118 - International Bearded Vulture Monitoring), which produced 67 fledglings, and 11 in Andalusia (Spain) - but also a territorial expansion. Some areas of the Alps host breeding Bearded Vulture pairs for the first time in 150 years, and for the first time in 100 years, a wild Bearded Vulture hatched and fledged in the skies of Cantabria (Spain) thanks to the collaboration between the Fundación para la Conservación del Quebrantahuesos and the Cantabria and Aragón governments. Four pairs were recorded also in Corsica, and for the first time in five years, one chick successfully fledged.

A historical success brought the species back to Bulgaria, with the **release of three Bearded Vultures in Sliven** last spring. Unfortunately, only one of them, named Boev, is now flying over the Balkans.

The Cinereous Vulture – Europe's largest vulture

Aegypius monachus

NT NEAR THREATENED

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2025 in figures

- **10 colonies** actively monitored by the LIFE Aegypius Return in Spain and Portugal.
- **6 Cinereous Vultures** rescued and rehabilitated in Portugal were soft-released by the LIFE Aegypius Return
- **6 Cinereous Vultures** rescued and rehabilitated in Spain were translocated to Bulgaria and **released in the Rhodope Mountains** by LIFE Rhodope Vultures
- **First breeding pair** observed in the Eastern Rhodopes
- **47 breeding pairs and 27 successful fledglings** in Dadia-Lefkimi-Soufli Forest National Park in Greece
- **Record breeding season in Bulgaria** thanks to the Bearded Vulture project restocking programme, with 5 fledglings from 15 territorial pairs.

Conservation projects

- Bearded Vulture LIFE 2023-2030 – Balkans
- LIFE Rhodope Vulture 2024-2029 – Rhodope Mountains
- LIFE Aegypius Return 2022-2027 – Iberia – Portugal & Western Spain

Cinereous Vultures are Europe's largest raptor and top mountain–forest scavengers, feeding mainly on mammal carrion. Once widespread across southern and central Europe, **their numbers crashed in the 20th century** under illegal poisoning (e.g., predator baits), shooting, food scarcity, habitat loss, and anthropogenic disturbance. By the 1970s, the only remaining populations were located in Spain and in the Balkans, with few sparse individuals.

Thanks to legal protection and conservation actions, Spanish numbers have since rebounded. Today, ~2,740 pairs breed in Europe, the vast majority of them live in **Spain and Portugal**, where the species naturally recolonised their former distribution areas. Reintroduction projects have largely contributed to the recovery of the species in France and Bulgaria. Even though Cinereous Vultures are globally considered Near Threatened in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, they are a Least Concern species in Europe, except for Portugal, where they are still under the Endangered status. The key to this conservation success is international collaboration. Projects like the LIFE Aegypius Return in Iberia, the Bearded Vulture LIFE in the Balkans, and LIFE Rhodope Vultures in the Rhodope Mountains rely on a vast network of international relationships for the protection and the expansion of the species.

Despite successes, threats persist: poisoning (baits and veterinary toxins), lead ammunition (ingestion of shot pellets in carcasses), shootings, electrocution/collisions on power lines, and habitat disturbance remain serious.

2025 successes and challenges

In 2025, we began adequate monitoring of the **Cinereous Vulture colony in Serra do Mendro** (Portugal), which was discovered in 2024 by ICNF. This new colony, with 15 nests in 2025, could be a strategic breeding nucleus for the species in Iberia, but it is already under strong pressure from several renewable energy production projects planned for the area.

In the summer, **severe wildfires** affected the Douro International Natural Park, destroying six Cinereous Vultures nests and some of the infrastructures built by the LIFE Aegypius Return project, including the infirmary and logistics centre supporting the acclimatisation aviary and the supplementary feeding site.

On a brighter note, the LIFE Rhodope Vulture project **released the first six Cinereous Vultures** of its programme in Eastern Rhodope Mountains, while the Dadia-Lefkimi-Soufli Forest National Park in Greece colony, in Greece, celebrated 41 breeding pairs and 27 fledglings, the **highest population record** since the wildfire in 2022.

The Bulgarian population reached its **highest reproductive record** with 5 chicks and 15 territorial pairs. The population has been supported over the years by the Bearded Vulture LIFE project that works in collaboration with VCF and Junta de Extremadura on a restocking programme.

The Egyptian Vulture – Europe's only globally endangered vulture

Neophron percnopterus

EN ENDANGERED

©Bruno Berthemy

We contribute to Egyptian Vultures conservation through:

- Improved food availability
- Threat mitigation and prevention

Some of the projects we lead and join have a positive impact on the conservation of this species. In particular:

- BalkanDetox LIFE
- WildLIFE Crime Academy
- LIFE Aegyptius Return
- LIFE Safe for Vultures

The Egyptian vulture is Europe's smallest vulture and its only **full long-distance migrant**.

Adults have distinctive white plumage with a yellow face and a wedge-shaped tail (juveniles are brown). They feed mainly on carrion but also on insects, small reptiles, mammals, birds, and eggs, which they crack open with stones and sticks.

The species is classified as **Endangered** in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, reflecting catastrophic declines: Europe's population has fallen by ~50% in recent decades (about an 80% crash on the Balkan flyway) and only ~80% of the survivors now nest on the Iberian Peninsula. Small, isolated groups remain in France (~70 pairs), Italy (~10 pairs), and the Balkans (~60–80 pairs).

Major threats include loss of habitat and food supply, poisoning (pesticides and illegal baits), and electrocution on power lines, as well as illegal shooting. All the conservation and protection measures deployed to protect other species of vultures around Europe are also beneficial to this species:

insulating electric lines and pylons, monitoring, anti-poisoning dog units' patrols, and legal protection measures.

2025 successes and challenges

In 2024-2025, the Egyptian Vulture population wintering in Cáceres (Spain) saw a **significant increase in numbers**. This is not an isolated phenomenon. In fact, the area saw a slow and steady increase in population in the past ten years. These observations confirm that **Cáceres** is becoming a key area for the species' survival in Spain.

In the middle of the Mediterranean, an Egyptian Vulture pair stole the spotlight. For the seventh year in a row, this solitary couple chose the **Sardinian coasts** (Italy) to raise their chick. This regular addition to the Vultures population in Sardinia confirms that the **conservation measures** applied on the Island have positive effects not only on the target species – Griffon Vultures – but on the entire ecosystem, making the Island a **hotspot for vultures** in the Mediterranean.

The Griffon Vulture – Europe's most social vulture

Gyps fulvus

LC LEAST CONCERN

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2025 in figures

- **1275 Griffon Vultures** recorded in the Balkans
- **37 Griffon Vultures** reported in Cyprus
- Over **500 vultures** were recorded in **Sardinia**, with a 21.03% increment in population compared to 2024, and a 14.3% increment in the number of breeding pairs.
- **29 Griffon Vultures** released in Sardinia by the LIFE Safe for Vultures
- Croatia approved a **historical 10-year management plan to safeguard Griffon Vultures**

Conservation projects

- LIFE Safe for Vultures 2021-2026 – Sardinia (Italy)
- LIFE SUPport 2023-2027 – Croatia
- LIFE With Vultures 2019-2025 – Cyprus

The Griffon Vulture is the most social vulture species in Europe, feeding, roosting, and breeding in **large colonies** that can host hundreds of individuals. They are well adapted to long soaring flights and search in groups over extensive areas for carcasses, relying on their sight to find food. Once they find it, they feed mainly on the softer parts of carcasses. Despite being extremely social and living in large groups, Griffon vultures are monogamous and pair for life. They prefer warm climates and are usually found in shrublands, grasslands, cliffs, and rocky slopes.

Throughout the 20th century, Griffon Vulture populations across Europe suffered severe declines driven by deliberate persecution, the reduction of wild ungulate populations and extensive livestock breeding, and especially the widespread use of poison baits. In more recent years, thanks to multifaceted conservation measures, European populations have experienced **a more than one-third increase**, with dramatic recoveries in Spain, France, and Portugal.

Today, the Griffon Vulture is Europe's most populous vulture species, with approximately 35,000 breeding pairs.

Despite the overall positive trajectory in Western Europe, significant threats remain.

Poisoning, electrocution, and collisions with electrical infrastructure are the most critical ongoing threats to this species.

Reintroduction and restocking programmes, supplementary feeding stations, anti-poisoning campaigns, and power line mitigation have all contributed to the broader European recovery and remain the cornerstone of ongoing conservation efforts.

2025 successes and challenges

Griffon Vultures experienced **unprecedented growth**. Croatia counts a record of 173 breeding pairs. In Sardinia, the latest census data show a 21.03% increment in population compared to 2024, and a 14.3% increment in the number of breeding pairs. These data testify to the positive effect of the projects' actions to protect and support Griffon Vultures. The data from the annual census in the Balkans in November revealed a constant increase in population, which now counts almost 1300 individuals.

In Croatia, the LIFE SUPport project conducted a study on **ecosystem services** provided by vultures. The results confirmed their role as a driver for the local economy. In addition, the Croatian government approved a historical **10-year management plan to safeguard Griffon Vultures**.

In Cyprus, the LIFE With Vultures project came to an end on a hopeful note. The project efforts **prevented the local extinction of the species** and built a foundation for it to persist despite threats and isolation.

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The Rüppel's Vulture – Europe's fifth and newest vulture species

Gyps rueppelli

CR CRITICALLY ENDANGERED

©Elly Miller

2025 in figures

- **2 Rüppel's Vultures** tagged in Morocco by JBel Moussa Raptor Rehabilitation Centre with our GPS trackers
- **1 Rüppel's Vulture found dead** in Southern Portugal

The Rüppell's vulture is a large African scavenger now increasingly recorded in southern Europe.

The juveniles of this species look similar to the Griffon Vulture. The two species often follow the same migratory routes in Africa and sometimes from Africa to Europe. The adults are quite distinctive, with pale spots all over their greyish plumage. Like Griffon Vultures, Rüppell's vultures live, feed, nest, and migrate in large groups, and are **adapted to long-distance flights**.

Once common all over the Sahelian fringe and the open savanna regions of East Africa, Rüppell's vultures have declined steeply since the 1990s, mostly threatened by habitat loss, illegal poisoning, and poaching for belief-based uses. They are now listed as **Critically Endangered** in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species.

Remarkably, since the 1990s, **Rüppell's Vultures have begun appearing in Europe**. Initially seen only as rare vagrants in Iberia, sightings have jumped in the 2010s–2020s. Every year, young Rüppell's Vultures join Griffon vultures migrating from their non-breeding areas in Western Africa,

with over a hundred individuals reaching Northern Morocco, of which some dozens cross into the Iberian Peninsula.

Over the last few years, this species has been recorded in most feeding stations in Andalucía (Spain). For this reason, Spain included the species in their list of vultures already in 2019, making the Rüppell's Vulture the **fifth vulture species in Europe**.

Several breeding attempts involving mixed pairs of Rüppell's Vultures and Griffon Vultures have been recorded in 2021-2022, and at the end of 2022, the **first chick of a mixed pair** fledged successfully, marking the first confirmed case of successful breeding of the two species in the wild (Muñoz et al., 2023). This event fuelled the debate over the future of the species in Europe, as concerns over "genetic amalgamation" with Griffon Vultures could lead to extinction. The phenomenon is still new and requires further observation.

At the same time, it is vital to implement and support conservation measures in the historical habitats of this species.

Rüppell's Vultures conservation actions we contribute to

We collaborate with **JBel Moussa Raptor Rehabilitation Centre**. This year, two individuals have been equipped with GPS trackers provided by the VCF in Morocco during their migration.

One individual, tagged by Jbel Moussa Raptor Rehabilitation Centre in cooperation with GREFA, in northern Morocco, was unfortunately found dead in Southern Portugal during the spring. The authorities suspect a poisoning incident.

Our work for vulture conservation

The Vulture Conservation Foundation is the world's leading wildlife organisation solely dedicated to protecting, conserving and restoring Europe's four species of vultures.

Our work includes *in situ* and *ex situ* conservation activities, starting with **research and threat identification**, to understand what drove each specific population towards unhealthy numbers, and following with **threat management, captive-breeding, reintroduction and monitoring** released individuals to restore and protect vulture populations in their historical habitat.

We cooperate with national and international organisations, keeping a vast network of experts ready to support vultures at any time. A large part of our work is also collaborating with governments and police forces to establish national conservation guidelines and plans.

Captive breeding

When a wild species is at risk of becoming extinct in its natural habitats, one of the conservation strategies that can help reverse the process is to **captive-breed individuals in controlled environments** and **reintroduce** their offspring. Alongside tackling threats and improving vultures' natural habitats, captive breeding plays a pivotal role in facilitating successful species restorations and reintroductions, reinforcing vulnerable populations, and ensuring the genetic health of the species.

There are different forms of captive breeding programmes; the European Endangered Species Programme (EEP), accredited by the European Association of Zoos and Aquaria (EAZA), is the most intensive type of captive population management of a species. Three of Europe's four species of vultures have an EEP captive breeding network.

Our contribution to the Bearded Vulture Captive breeding network

With over 40 years of experience, the Bearded Vulture EEP is coordinated by the Vulture Conservation Foundation on behalf of EAZA.

In 2025, the EEP captive-breeding network reared **24 Bearded Vulture chicks**, and **17 of them have been released into the wild**. The breeding success was lower than in previous years. Nevertheless, continuous monitoring of adult birds and chicks, and constant information exchange among centres and zoos have proven to be crucial for **reducing mortality and managing challenging situations**.

One of the biggest challenges the Bearded Vulture EEP faced this year was the emergence of **new diseases and parasites**. In both cases, the approach followed strict scientific protocols. Infected birds were isolated when possible, and biological samples were collected and analysed to find the best treatment available.

Vallcalent

We manage the **Bearded Vulture Specialised Breeding Unit at Centre de Fauna Vallcalent** following an agreement with **Generalitat de Catalunya**. This unit is specialised in **artificial incubation** and works with pairs and individuals that struggle to reproduce in other captive-breeding entities within the EEP.

Our expert Alex Llopis collaborated in the Bearded Vulture Reintroduction Project in the Alps for the release program, from 1986-89 in Austria and from 1991-1994 in Switzerland. He has coordinated the Bearded vulture European Endangered Species Programme since 2017. His expertise is crucial in helping individuals and pairs that have trouble adapting to the EEP and improving their chances of breeding successfully.

Among the special cases hosted at Vallcalent, there is **Kajazo**, a human-imprinted Bearded Vulture. Even though he unfortunately only recognizes humans as his own species, and therefore he can't be paired with another vulture, he demonstrates to be an incredible foster parent for Bearded Vulture chicks.

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2025 highlights

In 2025, the unit hosted an **intensive workshop for Bearded Vulture experts** to transfer their care expertise to professional wildlife rehabilitators across Europe and strengthen the Bearded Vulture conservation network.

Currently, Vallcalent houses **31 birds, with 6 active breeding pairs** and 3 pairs that could potentially breed in the foreseeable future.

Guadalentín

We manage the **Bearded Vulture captive breeding centre at Guadalentín**, following an agreement with the **Junta de Andalucía**. This centre plays an instrumental role in the conservation of Bearded Vultures, breeding and raising many chicks that will be reintroduced in Andalusia and other regions across Spain, France, and the Alps.

It specializes in **double and even triple adoptions**. It takes in chicks from other Bearded Vulture EEP partners and creates the best conditions for Bearded Vulture foster parents to raise them as their own. This approach ensures that the chicks behave like their wild counterparts when they grow up, allowing them to survive in the wild and breed once they become sexually mature.

In addition, the location of the centre – **up in the mountains of Sierras de Cazorla Segura y Las Villas Natural Park** - creates the best climatic conditions for Bearded Vultures.

The expertise of the team and the climatic conditions of the centre make it the perfect place to raise chicks hatched by the **most relevant founder birds from the entire EEP**, and ensure that the most important bloodlines within the EEP are kept safe.

Junta
de Andalucía

©Eleni Karazina

2025 highlights

In 2025, the captive breeding centre at Guadalentín raised **7 chicks**, entrusting them to **4 Bearded Vulture foster pairs**. Four of them have been released into the wild.

At the end of the year, the centre started a renovation process to further improve the housing conditions of its resident Bearded Vultures.

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Reintroduction, translocation and restocking

Further to the release of captive-bred vultures, one crucial step for species recovery in Europe has been the **translocation of vultures from healthy populations** to either restore populations in areas where they have gone extinct or to reinforce existing threatened populations.

For over 30 years, we have been working with partners around Europe, translocating wild-hatched rehabilitated birds from one more abundant population in one country to a smaller population in another country, or releasing captive-bred individuals to restock or reintroduce vulture populations in their historical habitats. We take part in numerous reintroduction and restocking projects for Bearded, Cinereous, and Griffon vultures around Europe.

Together with our local partners, we select the most appropriate release technique depending on the needs of each species and the characteristics of the release area.

Before their release, all birds are **equipped with GPS transmitters**, enabling us to closely track their movements and monitor their behaviour. GPS monitoring not only informs conservation actions and scientific studies but also allows for prompt response in case of an emergency.

Preparing the birds for their life in the wild

Hacking: placing a minimum of **two young vultures together in an artificial nest** in the release area and feeding them without any human contact until they **autonomously fledge and leave the nest**. This technique is particularly successful since it **mimics the natural development** of the birds in their nest. It is frequently used with young Bearded and Cinereous Vultures.

Delayed release: keeping **juvenile vultures in groups within an aviary** in the release area for a year after they fledge. In this way, they slowly get acclimatised to their surroundings and build strength and social bonds with their peers. It is used with **long-distance migratory species**, like the Egyptian Vulture, to delay their first migration until their second year of life, ensuring they are strong enough to migrate successfully.

Soft-release: is used in **translocations of rescued and rehabilitated** (usually young) vultures to new areas to restore or reinforce threatened populations. The birds are kept in an **acclimatisation aviary for several months before the release**, so they can bond with other individuals, observe conspecifics in the feeding area facing the aviary, and adjust to local conditions, which will increase chances of the birds staying within the release area as well as their survival in the new environment. It is often used in translocations of Cinereous and Griffon vultures from Spain to populations in other countries.

Bearded Vulture

Bearded vultures have been reintroduced for the **first time in Europe in Austria in 1986 by the Alpine Reintroduction Project**. The species was declared extinct in the wild in various parts of Europe during the 20th century, mostly due to active persecution driven by false beliefs and wildlife-human conflict.

The alpine reintroduction was a pioneering action that brought together an international network of experts and set the example for all the reintroduction and conservation projects of the species in Europe.

Map of Bearded Vultures distribution in Europe.
In bold, the areas where we contribute to Bearded Vulture reintroductions

Alps

Between 1986 and 2025, together with our partners, we released a total of **264 juvenile Bearded Vultures into the Alps**.

Today, there are around 450 Bearded Vultures, including **over 100 breeding pairs**. Between 1997 and 2025, at least 589 chicks fledged in the wild, **67 only in 2025**.

Andalusia

We teamed up with the **Junta de Andalucía** and the former Fundación Gypaetus to reintroduce the species in Andalusia by releasing captive-bred birds at different territories — Sierras de Cazorla, Segura, Castril and Las Villas. A total of **102 Bearded vultures** have been released in Andalusia since 1996, 6 of them this year.

Esperanza, the first wild-hatched chick since the start of the reintroduction programme, raised her first chick in the wild this year.

Bulgaria

The last Bearded Vulture soared over Bulgaria in 1972 in the Sinite Kamani Nature Park.

More than 50 years later, we have been proud to contribute to the work of the **Bearded Vulture LIFE project** (2023-2030), led by **Green Balkans**, by coordinating the historical release of **3 young Bearded Vultures** in Sliven in the Sinite Kamani Nature Park. Unfortunately, one of them died of a bacterial infection only a few weeks after the release, and a second one is under veterinary care. Only one of them, **Boev**, is exploring the Balkans under the careful monitoring of the project team.

Corsica

The Bearded Vulture population of Corsica is **one of the last existing autochthonous populations in Europe** and the last surviving genetic pool of a former meta-population including Sicily, Sardinia, Corsica, and the Alps.

To secure the survival of this unique population, we teamed up with **Parc Naturel Régional de Corse** and other international partners to **address local threats, restock the local population** with captive-bred birds, increasing local genetic variability, and **include some wild-hatched Corsican birds in our Bearded Vulture Captive Breeding Network EEP**.

The releases started in 2016 and are carried out every two years. Last year, together with the LIFE GypRescue project (2021-2025), we released 2 individuals in the area. Finally, after 4 years of failures, in 2025 Corsica celebrated a **wild-hatched fledgling** that successfully started its new life in the wild.

Maestrazgo

The Maestrazgo region of Valencia (Spain) was historically a breeding site for Bearded Vultures, and its population is crucial to **bridge the populations in the Pyrenees in the north and Andalusia in the south**.

For this reason, in 2018, we started reintroducing Bearded Vultures together with the **Generalitat of Valencia**, in collaboration with the **Autonomous Communities from Aragón and Catalonia, the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fish, Food and Environment** on a series of conservation actions. In 2025 we released 2 birds.

Massif Central and French Pre-Alps

With the Alpine population firmly re-established, the Pyrenean population saturating, and the Andalusian population growing, it's crucial to **connect the Alps and the Pyrenees**. The reintroduction of Bearded Vultures in the Massif Central and Pre-Alps area will promote the exchanges among different populations and improve each population's genetic diversity.

The first release took place in 2010, thanks to our collaboration with the Bearded Vulture EEP and local partners. A few years later, we joined the **LIFE GypConnect project** (2015-2022) led by Ligue pour la Protection des Oiseaux (LPO), followed by the **LIFE Gyp'ACT** (2022-2028). This year, we released **5 Bearded vultures** in the area.

©Bruno Berthemy

Cinereous Vulture

Reintroduction programmes in the Balkan Peninsula

In the early 19th to early 20th century, the Cinereous Vulture was widespread in the Balkans. Unfortunately, intensive **poisoning, habitat loss, and reduced food availability** drove the species to the brink of extinction.

By the 1970s–80s, only a single wild colony remained in the **Dadia–Lefkimi–Soufli National Park in Greece**.

The **Vultures Back to LIFE** project started a reintroduction programme in Bulgaria in 2015, with our technical contribution.

From 2018 to 2022, the project team released around **70 young Cinereous Vultures** in various regions of the Balkan Mountains. Most of these birds are wild-hatched vultures translocated from Spain, donated by the **Junta de Extremadura** and the **Junta de Andalucía**, and rescued and rehabilitated by **AMUS**.

In 2022, the first reintroduction programme in the **Eastern Rhodope Mountains** happened.

Two years later, the **LIFE Rhodope Vulture** started a **cross-border conservation programme** that aims to build a new Cinereous Vulture colony in the Bulgarian Eastern Rhodopes, while contributing to the protection of the last native Cinereous Vulture colony of the Balkans in the Dadia–Lefkimi–Soufli National Park, and improve overall connectivity between colonies of the species in the region.

In 2025, the project released **13 Cinereous Vultures**, thanks to the collaboration with GREFA, and the Junta de Andalucía.

Griffon Vulture

Reintroduction programmes in the Mediterranean

Sardinia

This Griffon Vulture population in Sardinia is the **last autochthonous breeding population of Griffon Vultures in Italy**.

The Griffon Vulture was a common species in Sardinia up to the late 1940s. After the Second World War, the species dropped rapidly due to the large use of **poison baits**.

In the 80's, there were only about 20 pairs, all breeding in the **north-west of the island**.

The translocation efforts to restore the Griffon Vulture population in Sardinia began in the 80's. Unfortunately, in the late '90s and early 2000s, three catastrophic poisoning events made the population plummet again, reaching the lowest number of breeding pairs ever recorded in the region.

From 2015, with our direct contribution, the **LIFE Under the Griffon Wings** project released more than **60 individuals in north Sardinia** and worked on **mitigating threats** such as **poisoning and electrocution**. When the project ended in 2020, the local population counted about **250 Griffon Vultures**, with around 50 breeding pairs.

A year later, the **LIFE Safe for Vultures** project took over to ensure the long-term survival of the species and to guarantee its **expansion towards the centre and the south of the island**. We are partners of this project as well, together with the **Junta of Extremadura** and **AMUS**. In 2025, **32 Griffon Vultures** were released in southern Sardinia.

Cyprus

Cyprus was once home to a thriving Griffon Vulture population. However, between the '60s and 2010s, their numbers dwindled significantly due to factors like **illegal wildlife poisoning, changes in farming practices, and nest disturbances**. By the early 2010s, only 10 to 12 Griffon Vultures remained, putting the species in imminent danger of extinction.

In response to this crisis, in 2011, the Project **GYPAS** started protecting the species. It introduced **25 Griffon Vultures from Crete** to bolster the local population, preventing immediate extinction. Despite the efforts, the local vulture population remained vulnerable.

In 2019, the **LIFE with Vultures** project was launched. The main actions of this project include **restocking the Griffon Vulture population** by importing birds from Spain, **improving food availability, and reducing the risk of electrocution and poisoning**. Thanks to our collaboration with **Junta de Extremadura**, young wild Griffon Vultures rescued in Spain are translocated to Cyprus within the LIFE with Vultures restocking programme.

The project came to an end in 2025. It saved the Griffon Vulture population on the island from local extinction. Nevertheless, many threats are still taking a toll on the population, especially electrocution and collision with energy infrastructure.

Synchronous movements of Cinereous Vultures Almeirão (orange) and Arçã (yellow) on 27/04/2025, 05/06/2025 and 20/07/2025. ©LIFE Aegyptus Return

Monitoring

Close monitoring is crucial for understanding the outcomes of conservation actions and guiding future efforts. Monitoring helps to understand the species **behaviour and habits**, the areas where individuals spend most of their time, where they feed and nest. All this information guides conservation actions and contributes to **identifying potential threats**.

Some monitoring techniques, like GPS tracking, can also provide data on the individual's health status and behaviour, alerting the monitoring team in case of emergencies.

We use different techniques to monitor both resident and reintroduced birds. Some birds receive **coloured rings** on their legs, or have some **feathers bleached in a precise pattern**; others are also equipped with lightweight **GPS transmitters**.

All the collected data are shared with our partners at local conservation projects and help the entire conservation community learn more about the European Vulture species.

Every year, we equip the birds we release with GPS transmitters in collaboration with our partners. In addition, we deploy several transmitters to **monitor wild hatched individuals in Europe, Morocco** – where we work on Rüppell's Vultures conservation with JBel Moussa Raptor Rehabilitation Centre - and **Central Asia**. In 2025, we provided GPS transmitters to tag young Cinereous Vultures in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan to help track their movements, providing critical data for the species conservation.

International Bearded Vulture Monitoring Network

The International Bearded Vulture Monitoring Network (IBM) is a **unique collaborative effort** led by us at the Vulture Conservation Foundation. It involves 24 full partners and 4 associated organisations (NGO's, National and Natural parks, government organisations). Its mission is to **monitor and safeguard** the Bearded Vulture population in Europe.

The IBM Network, with its collaborative approach, **collects, shares, and disseminates data** on Bearded Vultures, fostering global discussions on conservation strategies.

It also organises and manages the **International Bearded Vulture Observation Days (IOD)**. The initiative, held in October, involves experts and volunteers around Europe in **simultaneous counts**, contributing vital data for an accurate population demography assessment across European regions.

2025 in figures

- **Over 100 breeding pairs** were recorded in the Alps, breaking the three-figure number for the first time.
- The IBM network expanded, increasing its number of partners to 24 (19 partners in 2024) and expanding the monitoring area to include Bulgaria.

IBM 2025 partners

Associated organisations

Funding partners

Tackling Threats

To preserve vulture populations in Europe, we can't ignore the threats that drove them close to extinction and that are still taking a toll on them today.

We are committed to mitigating threats through **actions tailored for each species and territory**, developed in solid collaborations with local partner NGOs and governments, and implemented through comprehensive projects (e.g. LIFE).

Vultures are umbrella species; protecting them means taking care of entire ecosystems. Every project we manage or take part in addresses these threats either on a local or on an international level.

In recent years, our work has been mostly focused on tackling two of the biggest threats to vultures: **illegal poisoning**, and **electrocution and collision with electrical infrastructures**.

Powerline electrocution and collision:

When perched on dangerous pylons, vultures can touch **uninsulated wires** with their long wings and cause a fatal electric shock. This risk is preventable. Insulating high-risk electric poles or replacing them with more modern designs significantly reduces or eliminates bird electrocutions.

Moreover, while flying, **vultures cannot always detect obstacles ahead**, such as power lines, and collide with them with fatal outcomes.

Marking powerlines with high-visibility reflectors can successfully reduce the risk of collision.

The LIFE projects we take part in work alongside electricity companies to mitigate this threat within their target area.

Encroachment of energy infrastructure

The rapid expansion of **wind and solar farms** is increasingly encroaching on vulture habitats, **reducing and degrading suitable areas and increasing disturbance**, which is particularly critical near breeding colonies.

These massive structures can disrupt regular flight paths, leading to exclusion of vultures from key windy areas, but the cumulative impacts of energy infrastructure remain largely unknown.

Windfarms can also add to direct vulture mortality through **collision**, and recent research suggests that wind turbine blades should feature **highly contrasting black-and-white patterns** to make them visible for vultures and effectively reduce collision risk.

Illegal Wildlife Poisoning

The use of poisoning baits to **illegally control wild predators** (e.g., due to conflicts related to livestock predation) is far more common than we imagine, severely threatening wild and domestic animals. Unfortunately, obligate scavengers like vultures are often incidental victims of these criminal actions. Poisoning is, in fact, **the most severe threat to vultures** in Europe and beyond.

We lead **two international LIFE projects** that are completely dedicated to building knowledge and capacity for threat prevention and mitigation: the **Balkan Detox LIFE** and the **WildLIFE Crime Academy**.

The first one focuses on preventing and mitigating poisoning events in the Balkans. The second started as a branch of Balkan Detox LIFE and became an independent project in 2024 in collaboration with the Junta de Andalucía. It builds on the Spanish expertise on preventing and prosecuting crimes against wildlife to **train enforcers, prosecutors, and conservationists across Europe**.

In 2025, South Africa, Nigeria, and The Gambia saw a wave of devastating poisoning events fuelled by traditional beliefs. Over two hundred vultures were poisoned and killed in **five different criminal incidents over the summer**, including 100 Critically Endangered Hooded Vultures. We could not ignore these tragedies. Together with BirdLife International, the CMS Vultures Mou, and the Gambian government, we organised a **workshop to increase the capacity of national agencies** and NGOs in addressing wildlife poisoning events. During five days, we focused on how to identify, safely manage, and analyse a wildlife crime scene, and fitted a Hooded Vulture with a GPS transmitter to showcase how these birds can act as sentinels. VCF continues to support the local team, furthering their work on national wildlife crime action protocols together with the Gambian government and relevant local NGOs.

Analysis of power lines with collision risk for vultures, in the Douro Internacional Natural Park ©VCF

Poisoning from veterinary drugs

Some veterinary products used on livestock, such as the **Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drug (NSAID) diclofenac**, have devastating effects on vultures if ingested. Diclofenac, for example, has caused about a 95% decline of three Gyps species in India within less than a decade.

In Europe, the use of these substances is regulated, but unfortunately still encouraged.

Lead poisoning

When vultures feed on carcasses of **shot game animals**, they unintentionally ingest fragments of bullets and lead pellets.

Lead is a heavy metal; it is not processed by the body, but instead **it accumulates in the liver and in the nervous system tissues**, causing adverse effects on vultures' health and survival, and even causing death.

We encourage the **transition to lead-free ammunition**, working directly with hunters in Portugal with the LIFE Aegyptius Return project, in Croatia with the LIFE SUPport, in Sardinia with LIFE Safe for Vultures, and raising awareness in Italy.

We contributed to the international conference “Lead: a borderless poison” held in Italy on October 17-18, 2025. The conference confirmed that lead is a subtle **threat to vultures, ecosystems, and human health**. The effect of this poison can be devastating, and **it persists in the environment for decades**, contaminating the food chain. For this reason, the experts agreed that Europe should move towards banning lead from hunting ammunition and substitute it with safer alternatives that have already been successfully tested.

The Gambia mission crew ©VCF

© Bruno Berthemy

Research

Knowledge is the cornerstone of conservation actions. Understanding vultures' behaviour, ecology, and the threats they face is essential for designing effective strategies with a positive impact.

Our team contributes to **vulture research and data analysis** that is helping shape conservation actions for vultures in Europe and beyond. From feasibility studies guiding reintroduction initiatives to comprehensive movement analysis of GPS-tracked birds and evidence-based reasoned opinions on energy developments, our research spans diverse vulture topics. Together with our partners, our continued efforts on compiling long-term datasets on movement, breeding, mortality, and survival provide much-needed **evidence to inform management and conservation policies**, ensuring effective measures for the preservation of these essential species.

Ecosystem services studies

Ecosystem services are the wide range of **benefits that humans receive from healthy ecosystems**.

As obligate scavengers, vultures provide several of these services, including the consumption of livestock carcasses, which contributes to **nutrient recycling** and helps **regulate the spread of diseases**, while **reducing the direct financial costs and greenhouse gas emissions** associated with carcass disposal. Additionally, vultures are fascinating birds with **cultural significance**, contributing to human well-being while generating economic benefits for local communities through **ecotourism**.

In 2025, we contributed to the quantification and valuation of these ecosystem services provided by Griffon Vultures in Croatia (LIFE SUPport) and by Cinereous, Griffon, and Egyptian vultures in Portugal (LIFE Aegyptius Return).

Each of these studies revealed that, by consuming livestock carcasses within the project areas, a healthy vulture population annually **saves local communities several hundred thousand euros** in carcass transport and processing costs (14.000 € in Croatia, and 313.000 € in Portugal), and **up to 1200 tons of carbon dioxide emissions**, depending on the study area.

The cultural significance of vultures is as striking as their ecological role. Vultures have been part of **local cultures and folklore** for centuries, and nowadays they provide recreational services in the form of **ecotourism**, especially for birdwatchers and nature photographers. Vulture-related ecotourism generates **192-375,000€** in the project areas, significantly supporting the local economies.

These studies reinforce the notion that protecting vultures contributes to ecosystem health and human well-being, while also bringing financial benefits.

Although attributing an economic value to vultures' contributions is important to inform management, no economic label can fully capture the ecological, cultural, and symbolic importance of healthy, functional ecosystems, in which vultures play an essential role. Vultures – and biodiversity in general – real contribution to society far exceeds any monetary estimate.

Guidelines for energy development and reasoned opinions

We have issued over **40 technical reasoned opinions** for public consultations and direct inquiries about territorial land planning and energy developments planned in critical areas for Cinereous Vultures in Portugal.

All these opinions were based on data collected over the last decade, including vultures' breeding, feeding, and resting areas and on the extensive GPS tracking dataset of Cinereous and Egyptian vultures, to reveal flight corridors, dispersal areas, and estimate home ranges.

Building on this work, we developed a **practical, science-based framework to guide decision-making on wind farm planning and approval** in the proximity of Cinereous Vulture colonies in Portugal, focusing on safeguarding juvenile vultures during the post-fledging dependency period. We used GPS tracking data from 38 juvenile vultures tagged in their nests to estimate the progressive expansion of their home ranges during the dependency period and assess the overlap with circular buffers of increasing radius to determine optimal protection areas around the nests.

Link to the reports

- **Ecosystem Services in Croatia** - <https://zenodo.org/records/16902835>
- **Ecosystem Services in Portugal** - <https://zenodo.org/records/15866471>
- **Spatial guidelines for safeguarding Cinereous Vulture colonies from wind farm expansion** - <https://zenodo.org/records/17080823>

We presented three conservation scenarios:

- **Conservation First**, which maximizes protection and suggests a buffer radius of 21.3 km for juvenile vultures;
- **Compromise**, balancing protection with wind farm expansion under a protection buffer of 17.5 km;
- **Industry First**, which minimizes protection and favours wind farm construction, with a buffer radius of 7.7 km, offering minimal protection for Cinereous Vultures.

Cinereous and Griffon Vultures with a windfarm in the background ©Bruno Berthemy

The drivers behind Bearded Vulture breeding success in the Alps

Almost 40 years after the start of the Bearded Vulture reintroduction project in the Alps, this year, a research from D. Santos-Cottin, B. Arroyo, F. Loercher, A. Brambilla, and J. Terraube made use of the **comprehensive data** collected by the different IBM partners to analyse how Bearded Vultures are breeding across the Alpine range, and **what factors influence their reproductive success**.

Since the very first successful breeding event was recorded in 1997, the alpine population has seen a steady - but not evenly distributed – growth, reaching 65 breeding pairs and 42 fledglings in 2021.

Link to the study

- **The drivers behind Bearded Vulture breeding success in the Alps -**
<https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.70027>

The aim was to understand what factors **explain regional differences** in the number of breeding pairs and their success in raising young. Switzerland saw the largest increase in breeding pairs, with 65% of breeding success over an average of 60%.

The study revealed that **nest elevation, long-lasting pair bonds, and nesting within a protected area** positively influenced breeding success. The number of birds released in a region did not predict breeding success, but pairs formed by **wild-hatched parents showed a 30% higher breeding success** than mixed or fully captive-bred released pairs.

Bearded Vulture © Hansruedi Weyrich

Important areas for the Bearded Vulture in Corsica

A detailed understanding of the most important areas for Bearded vultures is crucial to **anticipate potential conflicts of land use** and guide decisions toward the **sustainable management of Corsica's natural heritage**.

In her *Master's internship* at VCF (*'Stage professionnel'*), Cécile Peyre integrated and analysed tracking data of non-territorial Bearded Vultures, as well as known nest locations and feeding sites.

The novelty of her work lies in the integration of these different data types into a **final map showing the Bearded Vulture utilization distribution in Corsica**. Movement models applied to the tracking generated utilization distributions for the non-territorial birds. Additionally, she produced projected (theoretical) utilization distributions within circular buffers around nests and feeding sites. The three data layers were then merged into a single operational map that can be used to guide the harmonization of energy projects with the conservation of Bearded Vultures.

Link to the studies

- **Important areas for the Bearded vulture in Corsica -**
<https://zenodo.org/records/15858323>
- **Raptor poisoning in Europe -**
<https://doi.org/10.3356%2Fjrr2373>

A comprehensive study on Raptor Poisoning in Europe

The study compiled and analysed **raptor poisoning incidents across 22 European countries over two decades** (1996-2016) – we contributed with data on vultures. The compilation documented **3,196 poisoning events**, impacting **4,437 raptors** spanning **37 species**.

Obligate and facultative scavengers are the most affected by poisoning events, with buzzards, eagles, vultures, and kites comprising 85% of the poisoned birds.

The study identified 41 pesticides used alone and 34 in combination.

Carbofuran and aldicarb were the most detected toxins. More alarmingly, over half of the poisonings with carbofuran and aldicarb occurred after these substances were banned from trade.

During the year, poisoning events are more frequent during **March and April**, coinciding with illegal predator control activities undertaken in several countries.

The study demonstrates that pesticide poisoning is still widespread in Europe. This criminal practice affects already endangered species and consequently damages entire ecosystems. Even so, most poisoning incidents often go undetected.

We coordinate two international LIFE projects dedicated to fighting wildlife poisoning: **BalkanDetoxLIFE** and the **WildLIFE Crime Academy**. Most raptor-related projects across Europe are also dedicating efforts to tackle this threat, demonstrating how impactful it is on obligate and facultative scavengers' populations and their ecosystems.

© Hansruedi Weyrich

Communication and Outreach

In 2025, we worked tirelessly to bring awareness about vulture conservation, share vulture species peculiarities, conservation stories, and showcase why vultures are essential for ecosystems, human well-being and economies.

In collaboration with our project partners, we highlighted our **collective field actions** and the **progress of vulture conservation** across Europe. We shared the challenges and threats vulture species face and how we support them.

We developed a **website** for our newest LIFE project, the WildLIFE Crime Academy, and implemented an innovative **knowledge exchange platform**. It fosters connections within the Academy and allows participants to discuss their everyday cases with the mentors and other members.

2025 milestones

- **158** news published on our website (+24% compared to 2024)
- **97,213** unique users (+23% compared to 2024)
- **723** Social Media posts
- **2M impressions**
- **+102% Instagram reach growth**
- **10K followers** reached on Instagram
- **+71%** interactions on Facebook
- WildLIFE Crime Academy **website and knowledge exchange platform**

International Vulture Awareness Day

Over the last two years, we have had the honour to manage the International Vulture Awareness Day: a day, the first Saturday of September, that the conservation community takes to **celebrate the hard work and the hard-won successes in vulture conservation.**

In two years, we expanded it from one day to a whole year of work and content creation to **inform, raise awareness, and celebrate** all vulture species and conservation activities dedicated to vultures worldwide.

In 2025, we recorded **144 events** linked to the International Vulture Awareness Day taking place in September all over the world. Talks, vulture conservation facilities tours, online events, and celebrations were held across **41 countries!**

We also organised, together with our partners, a **photography contest** with 38 participants who shared their vision of vultures through their incredible pictures.

Map of the events registered for the International Vulture Awareness day 2025 in the world.

LIFE Projects

We base our work on decades of expertise and on the best available science tailored to address the unique behaviour, ecology, threats, and habitats of each vulture species.

We are the **leading conservation organisation for vulture conservation** in Europe.

Our projects focus on the five species of vultures living in Europe: Bearded Vulture, Cinereous Vulture, Egyptian Vulture, Griffon Vulture, and the recently recorded Rüppell's Vulture.

Drawing upon our expertise in captive vulture breeding for conservation, as well as reintroduction and restocking efforts, threat mitigation, and the monitoring and tracking of wild vultures, we foster **collaboration** with governments, businesses, local communities, and fellow non-governmental organizations.

Together, we design and deliver **conservation projects across Europe**, working collectively to ensure the protection of vulture populations.

The LIFE Programme, initiated by the European Union in 1992, plays a vital role as a funding instrument for environmental and climate initiatives. It has co-funded over 4,500 projects that contribute to conservation efforts, green technology advancements, and climate action across Europe.

In 2025, we were involved in **ten LIFE projects**, coordinating three of them:

- LIFE Balkan Detox
- LIFE Aegyptius Return
- WildLIFE Crime Academy

Map of all the LIFE project we led or joined in 2025

BALKAN DETOX LIFE

Period	2020 - 2025
Area	Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Republic of North Macedonia and Serbia
Target species	Cinereous Vulture, Egyptian Vulture Griffon Vulture

BalkanDetox LIFE is **the first LIFE project we have led**. It started in 2020 and addresses the widespread issue of **illegal wildlife poisoning across seven countries in the Balkan Peninsula**. This practice, often aimed at predators like wolves and jackals, has had catastrophic side effects — killing vultures and other protected species along the way.

It is estimated that over 2,300 vultures have perished from poisoning in the past two decades in this region.

Sadly, **only a fraction of poisoning incidents is reported**, leaving the true impact largely undocumented, and making illegal wildlife poisoning the **top conservation concern** for various threatened species in the Balkans and in Europe.

This project's mission is to **raise awareness and strengthen national capacities** to combat this long-standing, deeply rooted conservation issue in *Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, the Republic of North Macedonia, and Serbia*.

The project also contributes to the monitoring of Griffon Vultures in the area through GPS tracking.

By following the movements of the birds, the project team can effectively track and prevent mass poisoning incidents of the species and other scavenging animals, as they would also act as sentinel species.

Since the first workshop in Madrid, the project has held **11 specialized sessions** for prosecutors and judges, and trained **164 participants**, strengthening regional collaboration and prosecution strategies.

One of the project's most transformative initiatives was the **Wildlife Crime Academy (WCA)**, developed with Spanish authorities. Forty-four professionals across the Balkans completed the full three-module course to become certified wildlife crime experts.

Graduates have since led national training programs, equipping over **570 police officers, prosecutors, veterinarians, and forestry officials** with the tools to investigate poisoning cases effectively in their own countries.

The BalkanDetox LIFE project has truly changed the game. It built bridges between governments, conservation groups, and local communities. It brought a hidden crisis into the light and turned it into a recognized crime. Most importantly, it gave institutions the confidence and resources to take action — and gave vultures a real shot at survival.

2025, time to draw conclusions

The Balkan Detox LIFE project is now close to its end. The closing conference saw the participation of around **85 experts, government officials, NGOs, and law enforcement representatives** across the Balkans. They came together to build on the project's achievements and reinforce future coordination in tackling wildlife crime.

Thanks to the efforts of the project team and local partners, each of the countries involved has developed some protection measures against poisoning incidents over the last few years.

In **Albania**, wildlife poisoning shifted from being ignored to being the only environmental crime with an official action plan. This is the result of strong institutional collaboration, which also led to the approval of investigation protocols, a formal chain of custody for evidence, and national training sessions. Albania developed and adopted **Standard Operational Protocols (SOPs)** as part of its National Anti-Poisoning Road Map, a national action plan.

In addition, in 2025, the Ministry of Tourism and Environment officially approved a long-term national "**Action Plan for the Protection from Poisoning of the Endangered and Endemic Species of Wild Fauna in Albania, 2025-2035**".

This plan includes detailed procedures for handling poisoning cases, designating responsible personnel, and collecting and processing evidence.

In **Bosnia and Herzegovina**, national training programmes have sparked deeper cooperation between institutions. Educational workshops led to a better relationship with prosecutors and judges. In addition, they developed their **SOP**, and their **national action plan** is ready and waiting for approval.

Croatia, with its long-running vulture conservation work, has integrated its SOP as official recommendations within its **National Action Plan against Wildlife Crime**.

Greece approved its SOP in 2022 and, over the years, made **significant progress in wildlife poisoning monitoring and management**: broader satellite tracking, protocol endorsements, and the expansion of anti-poison canine units. Collaboration with livestock breeders and widespread public campaigns helped prevent poisoning incidents.

In **North Macedonia**, training programmes created clear protocols and rapid-response systems. An informal but active **network of authorities** now works together consistently, and rural education campaigns have paid off.

Serbia made major strides, with the Ministry of Internal Affairs forming a separate **unit to suppress environmental crime**. It carried out three operations targeting illegal pesticide trade, resulting in multiple arrests and two convictions for wildlife poisoning.

Law enforcement, veterinarians, and prosecutors received targeted training, while **media campaigns** reached an astonishing 20 million people each year.

In 2025, **twenty-five vultures have been tagged** under the auspices of the BalkanDetox LIFE project, and a regional online monitoring platform has been established in each country. Over **160 GPS-tagged birds are now monitored across the Balkans**. It's clear that through the years, the response to poisoning has changed. Between 2000 and 2020, just 6% of poisoning cases led to investigations — and less than 1% ended in prosecution. Fast forward to 2025, and **65% of cases are now being investigated**, with more use of forensic necropsies and toxicology labs.

2025 milestones

- **Albania**: the Ministry of Tourism and Environment officially approved a long-term national "**Action Plan for the Protection from Poisoning of the Endangered and Endemic Species of Wild Fauna in Albania, 2025-2035**".
- **Croatia** is finalising its work on the National Action Plan against wildlife crime.
- **Bosnia and Herzegovina** finalised a set of national guidelines to help shape a strategy against wildlife poisoning.
- Three professionals from **Serbia** joined the Wildlife Crime Academy.
- The project held **6 National training courses** on wildlife crime investigation: one in Albania and five in Serbia.
- The project's **Closing Conference**, held in May in Serbia, brought together around 85 participants.

© Bruno Berthemy

LIFE AEGYPIUS RETURN

Period	2022 - 2027
Area	Portugal and Spain
Target species	Cinereous Vulture

LIFE Aegyptius Return is the second project we lead. It was launched in 2022 to **consolidate and expand the Cinereous Vulture population in Portugal and Western Spain.**

The project aims to **double the breeding population in Portugal** from 40 to 80 pairs, increase breeding success, downgrade the species'

national status from Critically Endangered to Endangered, and **enhance connectivity between colonies.**

To do so, it focuses on **habitat improvement, population reinforcement, and threat mitigation** across ten Natura 2000 sites along the Spanish-Portuguese border.

The project's main actions include **releasing birds** via the soft release method, equipping vultures with **GPS transmitters**, improving existing or creating new **nesting platforms**, establishing **feeding stations**, and enhancing habitat. In addition, the project addresses **illegal poisoning and lead poisoning** by building capacity, raising public awareness, and transitioning hunters to non-lead ammunition.

2025, a year of partnership, challenges and successes

The first milestone reached this year was the creation of the **first two private unfenced feeding areas for vultures** in Herdade da Contenda, in Portugal. These are the first of 56 planned areas across the country.

Feeding areas are crucial for sustaining local scavengers such as Cinereous and Egyptian vultures. A study carried out by the project in 2024, coordinated by the LPN (League for the Protection of Nature), showed that food shortages for necrophagous birds are widespread. Without sufficient food available, these scavengers struggle to reproduce and survive.

The summer, on the other hand, presented a major challenge. Massive **wildfires** caused a direct and significant impact on the recovery of the species in the **Douro Internacional Nature Park**. **Six Cinereous Vulture nests** from this isolated breeding colony were destroyed by fire. The acclimatisation aviary built in the area by the project was also severely damaged, and the supporting infirmary and logistics centre was completely charred.

At least **two chicks** of this already small, but strategic, colony lost their life in the fires.

The event generated a strong public response, which made it possible to resume the protection actions in the area. The support received in this hard time is the result of the positive relationship the project has built with local communities over the years.

A few months after the fires, the Douro Internacional Nature Park welcomed **six Cinereous Vultures**, rescued, rehabilitated, and released within the soft release programme held by the project in collaboration with the local partner Palombar.

Acer, a Cinereous Vulture chick, died following the wildfires in the Douro Internacional region in August 2025. ©Palombar

This release marks a crucial step in strengthening the transboundary Douro International colony, the smallest and most vulnerable in Portugal.

On a more positive note, the summer also brought successes. The project hit another success by reaching **58 Cinereous Vultures tagged since 2022**.

Towards the end of the year, another important milestone was reached in **bridging nature conservation and energy transition**. The project was invited to clarify some of the “myths of energy and the environment” in an event that brought together the main stakeholders in Portugal’s energy transition.

To date, the LIFE Aegypius Return project has produced over **forty scientifically grounded technical opinions** - 27 of them focus on the impact of energy infrastructures on vultures - incorporating GPS/GSM tracking data from dozens of tagged birds, nesting information, colony expansion forecasts, and impact assessments for proposed projects, along with recommendations for risk mitigation and reduction. Moreover, it published a report presenting clear data and **practical recommendations to guide the planning of new wind farms** to reduce risks for the Cinereous Vulture.

Energy transition represents a strategic ally in the fight against the climate crisis. However, the biodiversity crisis, which exacerbates the climate crisis itself, must not be overlooked. Cross-sector co-operation will be key to achieving true environmental, social, and economic sustainability.

LIFE Aegypius Return partners and stakeholders gathered at Herdade da Contenda ©VCF

Participation of the LIFE Aegypius Return project in EMER's 4th Transformer Station. ©EMER

2025 milestones

- The first **two private unfenced vulture feeding areas** were built in Herdade da Contenda (Portugal).
- **Six Cinereous Vultures** were reintroduced in the Douro International Nature Park (Portugal) by Palombar following the soft-release method.
- The project participated in an event with the main stakeholders in Portugal's energy transition, **bridging nature conservation and the energy transition**.
- The 2025 breeding season registered **119-126 breeding pairs** and **56 chicks**.
- The project produced over **40 scientifically grounded technical opinions**

Period	2025 - 2030
Area	Europe, the Caucasus, and North Africa
Target Issues	Illegal killing, Trapping, Poisoning, Poaching, and Trafficking of wildlife
Target species	Cinereous Vulture, Egyptian Vulture, Griffon Vulture, Bearded Vulture

Stemming from the Balkan Detox LIFE project, the WildLIFE Crime Academy is the **third and most recent LIFE project we coordinate**. This five-year initiative began in 2024 and aims to **address wildlife crime with a holistic approach**. It strengthens law enforcement on national and international levels, enhances international cooperation, and builds capacity to combat wildlife crime in *Portugal, Slovenia, Romania, Montenegro, Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt, North Cyprus, and Georgia*.

Through a series of **specialized training programmes, knowledge-exchange workshops, and collaborative efforts** with governmental authorities, NGOs, and forensic experts, the project seeks to **improve investigation and prosecution** processes for wildlife crime.

Wildlife crime is a significant threat to biodiversity, security, and economic stability. This includes poaching, poisoning, illegal trade, and habitat destruction. Such activities contribute to species decline, environmental degradation, and weakened governance structures and security.

Intentional poisoning is one of the most important threats to scavengers, vultures included, while poaching and illegal trapping impact songbirds and game species in regions like the Mediterranean and Balkans.

The project was launched for the first time in 2021 as a branch of the Balkan Detox LIFE project in collaboration with the Junta de Andalucía, Spain's Ministry for Ecological Transition (MITECO), and the Spanish Guardia Civil.

The Academy is built on a simple premise: **empower professionals to tackle wildlife crime** with the same seriousness and capacity applied to other forms of crime.

Between 2021 and 2024, within the Balkan Detox LIFE frame, the WCA ran five international training courses involving 66 professionals from 13 countries. Thanks to trained alumni leading their own national courses, over 650 additional professionals have now been trained.

2025, Starting on the right foot

The project started its activity in 2025 with a new course that trained **37 professionals from 9 different countries** and projects around Europe. Over three intensive days, they were trained in securing crime scenes, conducting forensic necropsies, collecting toxicological evidence, and managing wildlife crime investigations.

Later in the year, the project representatives joined 260 participants from across Europe at the **European Ranger Congress**. The congress was the chance to present and promote the project itself to a large group of conservation professionals. The project received a strong and positive response, which underscored both its relevance in the international scene and the urgent need for this initiative.

2025 milestones

- The project's **kick-off meeting** was held in Seville (Spain) and brought together authorities from Spain, Portugal, France, Slovenia, Montenegro, Serbia, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Romania, and beyond.
- The **first-level training course** was held at the International University of Andalucía in La Rábida and brought together **37 professionals from nine countries**.
- The **second-level training course** brought together **35 professionals**.
- Dedicated national meetings were held in Romania, Montenegro, and Slovenia to establish formal national working groups tasked with drafting national roadmaps and investigation protocols tailored to each country's legal and institutional context. Montenegro already adopted a national action plan.

©Hansuredi Weyrich

The LIFE projects we joined forces with

Conservation is a team job. We partner with many organisations around Europe within LIFE projects to target crucial vulture conservation objectives on national and international levels.

In each project, we bring our decades of experience in captive breeding, monitoring, and research, and our support in policy making.

In 2025, we gave our contribution to **seven LIFE projects** from the Alps to Bulgaria, Corsica, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy, and the Rhodope Mountains. We worked with Bearded, Cinereous, and Griffon vulture conservation teams on reintroductions, habitat restoration, and food availability, and we followed every vulture's adventure with a full heart.

Period	2023 - 2030
Area	Balkans (Bulgaria, Romania)
Target species	Bearded and Cinereous Vulture

The Bearded Vulture LIFE project builds upon the vulture conservation successes of previous LIFE projects conducted in the Balkans. From the reintroduction of Griffon Vultures to the comeback from extinction of the Cinereous Vulture, the project aims to expand the conservation efforts by **reestablishing the historical distribution of Bearded and Cinereous Vultures** in the Balkans.

The Bearded Vulture LIFE focuses on **habitat restoration** – improving nesting conditions for Cinereous Vultures – enhancing vultures' food sources and mitigating threats, especially **electrocution and wildlife crime**. It also monitors reintroduced vultures through satellite transmitters and promotes vulture conservation and education with events and workshops.

2025 milestones

- **23 Cinereous Vultures** arrived in Bulgaria from Spain, where they were rescued and rehabilitated, as part of the ongoing reintroduction programme.
- The project celebrated an **exceptionally successful reproductive season** for Cinereous Vultures in Bulgaria. 12 pairs and 6 successful fledglings marked a milestone for the conservation of a species that only a few years ago was absent from the country.
- The historical return of Bearded Vultures to Bulgaria after half a century. Thanks to the project efforts and the collaboration between the Vulture Conservation Foundation, the Ostrava Zoo in the Czech Republic, and the Green Balkans Captive Breeding Centre, **three young Bearded Vultures were released in Sliven** (Bulgaria) at the end of the spring. Unfortunately, one of them died shortly after due to a bacterial infection, one had to be recaptured, and only one, Boev, is now flying over the Balkans bearing on his wings the hopes and efforts of the entire conservation community.

Period	2022 - 2028
Area	French Pre-Alps and the Massif Central
Target species	Bearded Vulture

Building on the success of LIFE GypConnect, the LIFE Gyp'Act project aims further to consolidate the Bearded Vulture population in the region, ensuring **connectivity between the Pyrenean and Alpine populations**.

The project reintroduces young captive-bred Bearded Vultures from the EEP with the hacking method to Parc national des Cévennes, Parc naturel régional des Grands Causses, Parc naturel régional des Baronnies provençales, and Parc Naturel Régional du Vercors. Each released vulture is carefully monitored through GPS transmitters.

At the same time, the project tackles the main threats to vultures, namely **electrocutions, lead poisoning, and criminal poisoning**. Lastly, it ensures a continuous and safe food supply for vultures by managing several **supplementary feeding stations**.

2025 milestones

- The LIFE Gyp'Act joined the **WildLIFE Crime Academy network**, participating in the training cohort that started in 2025.
- Encouraging signs from Parc Naturel Régional du Vercors, where **two Bearded Vulture pairs** were recorded and **two wild chicks** hatched. They both successfully fledged, but one of them died a month later.
- **Five captive-bred Bearded Vultures from the EEP were released**, and four successfully took their first flight:
 - Two were released in Parc Naturel Régional du Vercors.
 - Three were released in Parc naturel régional des Grands Causses; unfortunately, one bird died before it fledged.

Period	2021- 2026
Area	Corsica
Target species	Bearded Vulture

Corsica is one of the last places in Europe where Bearded Vultures have never gone extinct. It represents, together with the Pyrenees, one of the **last surviving genetic pools of a former meta-population** that included Sardinia, Corsica, and the Alps.

The Bearded Vulture population on the island has suffered a **steep decline over the past 25 years** due to a combination of threats, including **low genetic variability, inbreeding, a significant decrease in natural food sources, and random demographic events** caused by the very low number of individuals. The population's **fragmentation and isolation** have further exacerbated these issues, making conservation efforts even more crucial.

In 2021, the Parc naturel régional de Corse (PNRC) launched the project to prevent the extinction of the Bearded Vulture in Corsica. The project **releases captive-bred Bearded Vultures**

and preserves genetics through **ex-situ conservation** actions. It works on enhancing food availability by establishing supplementary feeding sites, supporting livestock farmers, and releasing captive-bred mouflons. Additionally, it strives to reduce the risk of poisoning through awareness campaigns and to mitigate the hazards of collision and electrocution by identifying and securing dangerous power lines.

2025 milestones

- The project celebrated the **first-ever wild-hatched Bearded Vulture that hatched from a pair of captive-origin birds in Corsica, and the first wild-hatched chick that successfully fledged in four years** on the island.
- The project installed 5 cameras to **observe 5 different nesting sites**. This will improve our knowledge of the Corsican population and inform future research and conservation plans.

Period	2024 - 2029
Area	Rhodope Mountains (Bulgarian-Greek cross-border region)
Target species	Cinereous Vulture

The last Cinereous Vulture breeding pair of Bulgaria was documented near the Studen Kladenets reservoir in 1993. Since that day, the only remaining Cinereous Vulture colony in the Eastern Rhodopes survives in Greece, in the Dadia National Park.

In 2024, the Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds (BSPB), together with Rewilding Rhodope Foundation, launched the LIFE “Restoration of the Cinereous Vulture Population and Trophic Chain.” Rhodope Vulture, dedicated to the recovery of the Cinereous Vulture population in the vast cross-border Rhodope mountains, between Bulgaria and Greece.

The project creates the conditions for Cinereous Vultures to thrive in Bulgaria by **restoring the natural food chain**, establishing new populations of wild herbivores, **preventing wildfires**, and **mitigating human-wildlife conflict**.

In addition, it facilitates the creation of a new Cinereous Vulture colony in Bulgaria by **translocating individuals from Spain** and monitoring their movements and health. Lastly, it will contribute to the conservation of the Dadia National Park colony.

2025 milestones

- **13 Cinereous Vultures** were released in the Eastern Rhodope Mountains between April and November
- **3 Cinereous Vultures reproductive pairs recorded in the Eastern Rhodope Mountains**, each one of them containing one individual released by previous reintroduction programmes.
- The Dadia National Park colony broke its records. The monitoring activities identified **41 reproductive pairs. 27 wild-hatched chicks successfully fledged**, the highest number in three decades.

LIFE SAFE FOR VULTURES

Period	2021 - 2026
Area	Sardinia (Italy)
Target species	Griffon Vulture

Following the success of the LIFE Under Griffon Wings project, the LIFE Safe for Vultures project, led by the University of Sassari and funded by the EU's LIFE Programme, continues to **protect and support the Griffon Vulture population in Sardinia**.

It aims to consolidate the Griffon Vulture population in Sardinia and return it to its historical habitats across the entire island.

The project involves an array of targeted conservation actions, including expanding the **network of farm feeding stations** to the south of the island, **restocking the local vulture population** with individuals coming from Spain, and mitigating threats like **poisoning, collisions, and electrocution**.

2025 milestones

- The **feasibility study** for the reintroduction of Bearded and Cinereous vultures in Sardinia received a positive evaluation by an international panel of vulture experts.
- An ecosystem services study highlighted the value of Griffon vultures for the island ecosystems and economy.
- **33 Griffon Vultures have been released on the island** to restock the local population.
- An **Egyptian Vulture pair** successfully reproduced in Sardinia for the seventh year in a row, benefitting from the conservation actions put in place by the project.
- The **supplementary feeding station network has been expanded to South Sardinia**, and a new Griffon Vulture colony has been recorded in the area.
- The annual Griffon Vultures census counted 516-566 individuals, with the **population growing by 21% in only one year**, and expanding towards the south of the island.

Period	2023 - 2027
Area	Kvarner islands, Učka and Ćićarija (Croatia)
Target species	Griffon Vulture

The Kvarner Islands (Croatia) host the **last Croatian Griffon Vultures breeding colonies** with their unique breeding grounds on sea cliffs. The species was once widespread across the mainland, but **habitat loss, poisoning, and diminished food availability** reduced it to a little more than a hundred individuals.

Led by the public institution Priroda, the LIFE SUPport project started in 2023 as an urgent response to the dramatic drop in Griffon Vultures colonies across Croatia. It aims to **increase the local Griffon Vultures population** and reconnect it with those in the Alps and the Balkans. The project actions primarily address the critical threats to Griffon Vultures survival, such as **nest disturbance, food scarcity, poisoning, and electrocution**.

2025 milestones

- The project hosted several **workshops** directed at the local community. It addressed hunters, promoting the use of non-lead ammunition, and involved children in vulture-related activities in several schools.
- Croatia formally adopted a **10-year Management Plan with an Action Plan to safeguard Griffon Vultures**.
- A study on the **ecosystem services** provided by Griffon Vultures in Croatia, produced by the project, highlights the role of vultures in reducing livestock carcasses disposal costs and greenhouse gas emissions. On the Kvarner Islands, vultures are also key drivers of a thriving ecotourism industry.

LIFE with VULTURES

Period	2019 - 2025
Area	Limassol and Paphos (Cyprus)
Target species	Griffon Vulture

Griffon Vultures are the most endangered bird of prey in Cyprus. They are on the verge of **extinction** due to multiple threats, including **illegal wildlife poisoning, food scarcity, and collisions with power lines.**

The LIFE with Vultures project, led by BirdLife Cyprus, aims to protect this species and mitigate the threats it faces. Among the project actions are improving food availability through **supplementary feeding stations**, securing hazardous power lines with **bird diverters**, and preventing and **combating criminal poisoning.**

Thanks to our collaboration with Spanish authorities and NGOs, the project **restocked the local Griffon Vulture population** with individuals rescued and rehabilitated in Spain. Each released individual has been equipped with a GPS transmitter for monitoring purposes.

2025 milestones

- The project came to an end in July
- The **local Griffon Vulture population** remains small, but thanks to the project efforts, it is not extinct
- An **anti-poison dog** unit is now in place to mitigate illegal poisoning events and prevent casualties among vultures

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Governance

Our governance structure is designed to support strong strategic planning and smooth operations. The organisation is led by a Management Board made up of five dedicated professionals who volunteer their time to oversee and guide our work.

The Vulture Conservation Foundation (VCF) is an international NGO founded in 2009, with legal headquarters in both the Netherlands and Spain.

To define our conservation priorities and make informed decisions for Europe's vulture species, we also rely on the expertise of our **Advisory Board**. This group includes 11 specialists with deep knowledge of vulture conservation and the natural history of Europe's vulture species. Their voluntary support is essential to our mission.

At the core of the VCF is a team of **23 passionate staff members**. Their skills cover captive breeding, reintroduction, research, communication, finance, and more. Together, we are committed to safeguarding Europe's four vulture species and restoring their populations across the continent's skies.

The team behind every success we achieved this year

VCF Director
José Tavares

**Finance & Administration
Manager**
Alice Gama

**Finance & Administration
Officer**
Consuelo Benedetti

**LIFE Balkan Detox
Project Coordinator**
Uros Pantovic

**LIFE Aegyptius Return
Project Coordinator**
Milene Matos

**Necrobiome PhD
student**
Diana Vieira

Conservation Director
Jovan Andevski

Conservation Officer
Monica Frutos

**Science & Monitoring
Manager**
João Guilherme

**Bearded Vulture
Science & Monitoring
Officer**
Franziska Loercher

**Communications
Manager**
Eleni Karatzia

**Communications
Officers**
Iida Sirvio
Enrica Calò

**EEP & Vallcaient
BV Captive-Breeding
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Alex Llopis Dell

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Carmen Contreras
Eric Capdevilla
Sonia Cortada

**Guadalentín
BV Captive-Breeding
Coordinator**
Pakillo Rodriguez

**Guadalentín
BV Captive-Breeding
Officers**
Angel Ochotorena
José Martínez
Julian Moreno
Margarita Limon
Teodoro Sanchez

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Finance Overview

The VCF, as a non-profit organization, primarily relies on grant funding from the European Union's LIFE Programme. We are also grateful for the support we receive from sources such as foundations, zoos and generous donors.

The Stichting Vulture Conservation Foundation (VCF) financial accounts report is comprised of the consolidated balance sheet as of 31 December 2024 and the consolidated statement profit and loss for the year 2024, prepared in accordance with Dutch Law Book 2 Chapter 9 and the Guidelines of the Dutch Accounting Standards Board (RJ650). All amounts are in Euros.

The accounts report was prepared with the supervision and review by Countus Accountants (The Netherlands) and was approved by

the VCF management board on the 3rd of June 2025. Here we present a summarized version of the statements. Reading this summary is not intended as a substitute for the consultation of the consolidated financial statements.

Apart from the official accounts statements, we also present a summary of income and expenses organized by categories, according to the main activities of the VCF.

The following financial data refer to the year 2024 for reporting reasons.

Income

In 2024, the VCF had a total income of **€ 4.436.995**, of which **85% are linked with multi-year projects** (LIFE, Guadalentin, Swiss Foundation project-based funds). The installations received, defined in project funding contracts, are recognized as income against the actual costs incurred and reported over a longer period. The yearly results of all these projects carry over to the following year, until the end of the project.

The rest of the project income (**11%**) is linked to **annual projects**, whose yearly results close on an annual basis and are extracted to the profit & loss account. The remaining income of 2024 (**5%**) comes from **donations from zoos, other organizations, and individuals**. At the end of this summary, you can also consult a comprehensive list of donors.

Project income €	4.284.385
<i>LIFE projects</i>	1.370.579
<i>Swiss Foundation</i>	2.062.902
<i>Guadalentin</i>	353.115
<i>Bearded vulture EEP</i>	86.238
<i>Other projects</i>	15.800
Donations	152.610
Total income 2024	4.436.995

Expenditure

In 2024, the VCF had a total expenditure of **€ 1.906.491**, of which **95% are linked with multi-year projects** (LIFE programme, Swiss Foundation projects, Guadalentin). The costs incurred and reported in these projects include staff salary, travel, external assistance and subcontracting, equipment, consumables, and other costs, and, in the case of some of the Swiss Foundation-funded projects, installments for implementation of actions by other partners, under contract.

The remaining expenditure was linked to **annual projects (4%)**, and the remaining to management and administration expenses not eligible or related to project implementation (1%).

Project expenditure €	1.893.951
<i>LIFE projects</i>	1.383.196
<i>Swiss Foundation</i>	102.019
<i>Guadalentin</i>	336.614
<i>Other projects (Bearded vulture EEP captive breeding, breeding/release services, IBM database management, among other projects)</i>	72.122
Management and administration expenditure	12.540
Total expenditure 2024	1.906.491

Total income 2024

€ 4.436.995

Total expenditure 2024

€ 1.906.491

If we divide the total expenditure for 2024 by type (staff salary 37%, travel 6%, external assistance/services 11%, Equipment and Infrastructure 5%, Consumables and Other costs 12%, instalments/grants to organizations 28% and Office and administration costs 1%), the costs were divided in the following way:

Expenditure by cost type	
<i>Staff salaries</i>	695 990
<i>Travel</i>	116 492
<i>External assistance /Sub-contracting</i>	205 874
<i>Equipment</i>	103 142
<i>Consumables</i>	96 353
<i>Other costs</i>	142 895
<i>Grants/Installments NGOs</i>	533 205
<i>Salaries / payroll management</i>	2 881
Total expenditure 2024	1.906.491

Consolidated balance sheet as at 31 December 2024

Current assets	31 December 2024	31 December 2023
Debtors	243.543	101.960
Liquid assets	5.395.351	3.027.942
Liquid assets	5.638.894	3.129.901

Liabilities	31 December 2024	31 December 2023
Equity	961.968	862.256
Continuity reserve	700.000	550.000
Budgets for projects	3.913.976	1.633.703
LIFE projects	2.236.484	1.268.086
Other projects	1.677.492	365.616
Liabilities	62.951	83.943
Creditors	62.951	83.943
Total liabilities	5.638.894	3.129.901

Project Liabilities for 31 December 2024

LIFE projects	€	LIFE projects	€
1905 LIFE GypRescue	11.574	1970 LIFE WithVulturesCY	(21.409)
1925 LIFE Aegyptius return	218.680	1980 LIFE BalkanDetox	31.640
1935 LIFE BV Bulgaria	315.963	1985 WildLIFECrime Academy	951.655
1945 LIFE GypAct	292.479	1990 LIFE Safe for Vultures	251.069
1955 LIFE SUPport	84.528	1995 LIFE Rhodope Vulture	100.306
Balance at December 31			2.236.484

Other projects	31/12/2024
0940 Organizational sustainability fund	€
1000 Restoring the vulture populations in Europe	100.000
1100 Bearded Vulture breeding / release	726.221
1170 Bearded vulture Maestrazgo	90.000
1180 Bearded vulture Guadalentín	-
1200 IBM membership and management	44.444
1250 Bearded Vulture EEP	40.804
1600 CMS Vulture MsAP	-
1640 Vulture Conservation Global	(642)
1670 MAVA Illegal Killing Birds	450.000
1690 VCF OD	18.130
1730 Wildlife crime training Bulgaria	10.000
1740 Griffon Vulture Transports	-
1800 Egyptian Vulture conservation	(1.465)
Balance at December 31	1.677.492

For more information on each project, please visit our website at www.4vultures.org

Profit and loss account for 31 December 2024	
31 December 2024	
	€
Balance on closed accounts	109.641
Gross margin	109.641
Other income	152.610
Gross operating saldo	262.251
31 December 2024	
	€
Other salaries	(2.881)
Other costs	(8.481)
Sum of operating costs	(11.362)
Subtotal balance/saldo	250.889
31 December 2024	
	€
Sum of financial income and expenses	(1.178)
PNL Balance (31-12-2024)	249.712

List of funders and donors 2024

We would like to thank all the individuals and organizations who have supported the conservation work developed by the VCF. Your valuable contribution allowed us to continue to work this year for the conservation of vultures in Europe. Thank you!

Organisations

Alpinium - Zentrum Naturerlebnis Alpin	Parco Naturale Alpi Marittime
ASTERS	Parco Nazionale Gran Paradiso
Beauval Zoo	Schönbrunner Tiergarten Ges.m.b.H
Berufsverband der Zootierpfleger e.V.	Stadt Frankfurt am Main
Ente di gestione delle aree protette delle Alpi Cozie	Stichting Zie-Zoo
Envergures Alpines	Stiftung Pro Bartgeier
ERSAF Direzione Parco Nazionale dello Stelvio – Lombardia	Swiss Foundation
EU LIFE Programme "Generalitat Valenciana"	The Endangered Wildlife Trust (The EWT)
Grand Parc du Puy du Fou	Thoiry Peaugres Conservation
Helsinki Zoo	Tiergarten der Stadt Nürnberg
Junta de Andalucia	Tiergarten Heidelberg Ges.m.b.H.
LBV - Landesbund für Vogel- und	Vautours en Baronnie
LPO Grands Causses	Vienna Zoo - Tiergarten Schönbrunn
Ministry of Environment and Water of Bulgaria	www.eaglewatch.nl
Nationalparkrat Hohe Tauern	Zoo Dresden Ges.m.b.H.
Naturpärke Tirol	Zoologischer Garten Berlin AG
Naturschutz in Bayern e. V.	
Novacek Rene	
Ostrava Zoo	
Parc National de la Vanoise	
Parc National des Cévennes	
Parc National du Mercantour	
Parc Naturel Régional Corse	
Parc Zoologique de Montpellier	

Individuals

Ad Schellen
Andy McClelland
Anneque Machel
Arabelle Hurlstone
Ashleigh Bartlett
Audrey Tompkin
Aurelien Benbernou
Brittany Meade
Carrie Cameron
Cengiz Balci
Cristina Hanga
Daniel Bringolf
Danielle Williams
David Tarlo
David Wright
Devin Sandlin
Dieter Scholz
Dillon Martin
Dr. Helga Masoud Abd-Alwhab Masoud
Dustin Kaltman
Edwin Pettipher
Erik Wiechers
Fabian Frederik Hausmann
Fatima Ortiz
Frank Helderman
Hans Bal
Hendrik Merz
Hr J E C de Groot
Ineta Zēna
Jackie McCracken
Jacob Phillips
James Sawford
Jedediah Smith
Jeevesh Natarajan
Jennifer Fernelius
Jerusha Samuel
Jim Knight
John Cooter
John Sills
John Wild
Karen Melander
Katherine Rubin NP
Kayla Teays
Kimberley Horner
Louise Stinchcombe
Luna Arcana
Madison Amack
Mairwyn Leigh
Maisy Inston
Marcos Fischer
Marjolein Prijs
Matthew Fontaine
Maxwell McCurdy
Molly Foust
Nadine Moreby
Napoleon Bakker
Nico de boer
Nils Coleman
Obakeng Mokote
Ochoa Illustration
Petra Timmers
Philippe Constantin
Prencipe Raffaele
R Stuart Craig
Rex Freeman
Robert Davies
Sabrina Ragaller
Sills John
Simon Christopher Milnes
Simon Osborn
SoCal Herding
Tobias Angele
Viktoria Neumann
Watzka Heinz

A heartfelt *thank you*

All of this would not have been possible without our funders, partners, fellow NGOs, donors, and everyone who reads us and engages with us on social media.

We want to express our deepest gratitude to each and every one of you. We truly appreciate your support and cooperation. You played a key role in our achievements. We look forward to continuing this journey together, creating the conditions for vultures to thrive in Europe and beyond.

Thank you for being an integral part of our conservation efforts for 2025 and for many years to come.

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